

A Knowledge Graph for Chemical Safety

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Abstract

The "BioBricks-OKG: An Open Knowledge Graph for Cheminformatics and Chemical Safety" aims to revolutionize how chemical health and safety data is accessed and applied in the realms of cheminformatics and toxicology. By evolving the current BioBricks-AI system, this initiative seeks to rapidly furnish chemical health and safety insights through an expansive knowledge graph. This graph will weave together data from 60+ health and cheminformatics repositories, correlating chemicals with health hazards, testing methods, and several pertinent entities, thereby enabling AI-driven explorations for pioneering chemical testing and regulatory techniques.

The merit of this proposal goes beyond merely collating information. It addresses a pressing need in the cheminformatics and toxicology domain - the challenge of seamlessly accessing data. With many databases currently ensconced in siloed repositories, developers face barriers in tapping into these resources. BioBricks-OKG, leveraging ontology alignment, offers a remedy by facilitating the convergence of these databases into a unified, readily accessible knowledge graph.

For attendees, the practical implications are monumental. Whether you're striving to discern chemical hazards, spearheading new testing methodologies, or drafting chemical safety guidelines, this knowledge graph is poised to be your touchstone. It equips you with a single, consolidated resource that obviates the need to sift through myriad databases, thus streamlining research and application processes. Collaborative efforts with NICEATM further accentuate the graph's utility in crafting guidelines and evaluating chemical safety paradigms. Additionally, given BioBricks-AI's current traction with over 20 organizations, including esteemed entities like NICEATM and Johns Hopkins, adopting and integrating this graph into your workflows promises to be seamless.

Join us as we delve into the mechanics, potentials, and applications of this transformative knowledge graph, and discover how it can empower your endeavors in the cheminformatics and toxicology landscape.